

PRODUCTION OF 12- AND 18-HYDROXYSTEARIC ACIDS AND SOME USEFUL COMPOUNDS DERIVED FROM THEM

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12- & 18-Hydroxystearic acids have been prepared from castor and 'kamala' seed oils respectively using commercial nickel catalysts. Both the acids have been lactonised. Experimental details for the oxidation of 18-hydroxystearic acid, using potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid, for obtaining hexadecamethylene-1:16-dicarboxylic acid are reported.

Castor and kamala seed oils are the two major sources of 12-hydroxy- and 18-hydroxystearic acids respectively. These acids have been prepared in good yields by using commercial nickel catalysts. For the preparation of 12-hydroxystearic acid a concentrate of tri-ricinolein was obtained from castor oil. The hydrogenation of this material, either as such or in presence of a solvent, using Ruffert nickel catalyst or preferably Raney nickel catalyst, and subsequent hydrolysis and purification of the hydrogenated product furnished 12-hydroxystearic acid in a sufficiently good yield.

18-Hydroxystearic acid has now been prepared by the hydrogenation of kamolenic acid (Gupta, Sharma and Aggarwal, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 463) in alcohol solution in presence of nickel catalyst instead of platinum catalyst, used earlier (Aggarwal *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1948, 7B, 136). Both the hydroxystearic acids have been lactonised in benzene solution using *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as a catalyst by the method of Stoll and Rouve (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 1238) as modified by Toyama and Hirai (*Res. Rept. Nagoya Ind. Sci. Res. Inst.*, 1952, 8, 36) for the lactonisation of 14-hydroxypalmitic acid. The yield of lactone from 18-hydroxystearic acid was about 76% of the theoretical, but with 12-hydroxystearic acid, 7.4% yield could be obtained.

Favourable conditions for the oxidation of 18-hydroxystearic acid to hexadecamethylene-1:16-dicarboxylic acid, by using chromic acid in acetic acid solution or preferably potassium dichromate in sulphuric acid, have also been worked out. Gupta *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) carried out the above oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

12-Hydroxystearic Acid from Castor Oil

Tri-ricinolein in about 74% yield was obtained from castor oil by the method of Achaya and Saretore (*Analyst*, 1952, 77, 375). Hydrogenation in all cases was carried out in a Parr's medium pressure hydrogenation apparatus in which the temperature and pressure of hydrogenation could be controlled.

Hydrogenation without the solvent.—Tri-ricinolein (200 g.) was hydrogenated in presence of Ruffert nickel catalyst (8 g.) at 145°-155° at 220-400 lbs./sq. in. After 7 hours the iodine value came down to 5.7 which could not be reduced further. The catalyst was filtered off and the hydrogenated product was crystallised from ethyl acetate or alcohol, m.p. 85-86°; I. V. 3.8; acetyl value, 150.1.

Hydrogenation in presence of solvent.—Tri-ricinolein (200 g.) was taken in alcohol (600 c.c.) and hydrogenated in presence of Raney nickel catalyst (4 g.) at 300-400 lbs./sq. in. The temperature was first kept at 100°-110° and gradually raised to 150°. After hydrogenation for 3 hours, the iodine value was 2.8. The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent distilled off. The hydrogenated product had acetyl value of 155.4.

Fatty acids were liberated from the hydrogenated product by the usual saponification method, and were crystallised from alcohol or ethyl acetate, yield 85%, m. p. 81-81.5°, I. V. < 1. (Found: Acetyl value, 158.9; C, 71.8; H, 12.3. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$: acetyl value, 164; C, 71.94; H, 12.0 per cent).

18-Hydroxystearic Acid from Kamala Seed Oil

Kamlolenic acid (200 g.), isolated by the method of Gupta *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), was taken in alcohol (600 c.c.) and hydrogenated in presence of Raney nickel catalyst (4 g.) at 300-350 lbs./sq. in. at 90° for first three hours and then raising to 100° for a further period of 4 hours. The catalyst was filtered off and the hydrogenated acid was freed of the solvent. After crystallisation from ethyl acetate or ethyl alcohol it melted at 95-97°, I. V. 1.2, yield 90%. (Found: Acetyl value, 160.5; C, 71.85; H, 11.87. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$: acetyl value, 164; C, 71.94; H, 12.0 per cent).

Lactonisation of 18-Hydroxystearic Acid.—18-Hydroxystearic acid (10 g.) was lactonised in 0.15% solution in benzene, using *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as a catalyst by the method of Toyama and Hirai (*loc. cit.*). After the reaction the solution was successively washed with water, 2% sodium carbonate solution, again with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Benzene was distilled off and the residue was dissolved in 200 c.c. of *n*-hexane. The insoluble residue (0.8 g.) after crystallisation from benzene melted at 113-113.5°, and was dimeric lactone, M. W. 563. (Found: C, 76.23; H, 11.9. $C_{36}H_{68}O_4$ requires C, 76.53; H, 12.13 per cent).

From the filtrate, hexane was distilled off when 8.7 g. of the crude lactone was obtained. This was fractionated and 7.64 g. of a fraction boiling at 130°-140°/0.2-0.3 mm. was obtained. Sap. value, 197.4 (calc. 198.9); M. W. (cryoscopic), 280.8. (Found: C, 76.84, H, 12.14. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 76.53; H, 12.13 per cent).

If the lactonisation is carried out in a more concentrated solution, the yield of dimeric lactone increases.

Lactonisation of 12-Hydroxystearic Acid.—12-Hydroxystearic acid (10 g.) was lactonised as above. The benzene solution was freed of the sulphonic acid by washing with water and the solvent distilled off. The residue had an acid value 114.3. It was boiled with 200 c.c. of *n*-hexane when 3.8 g. of a solid, m.p. 81-82°, was obtained. Mixed m. p. with 12-hydroxystearic acid indicated it to be the original unchanged material. The hexane solution was washed with 2% sodium carbonate solution and then dried. The solvent was removed when about 6 g. of a semisolid material was obtained. This was subjected to vacuum distillation and 0.7 g. of a liquid material boiling at 174-76°/1-2 mm. was obtained; M. W. (cryoscopic), 283.6. (Found: C, 76.89; H, 12.13. $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 76.53; H, 12.13 per cent). The residue could not be crystallised from any solvent.

Hexadecamethylene-1:16-dicarboxylic Acid

A mixture of potassium dichromate (37.5 g.) and sulphuric acid (1:2, 187 c.c.) was warmed at 90°-95° and 18-hydroxystearic acid (25 g.) was added in small lots during one hour. The heating and continuous stirring were maintained for another 3 hours after which the temperature was slowly raised to 120°-125°. After heating for 4 hours, the reaction product was cooled and then diluted with a large volume of water. The separated solid (24.7 g.) was crystallised from acetone, yield 22 g., m.p. 123-24°; mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen, 123.3-124.5°.

The dicarboxylic acid in only 50% yield could be obtained by the oxidation of 18-hydroxystearic acid with chromic acid in glacial acetic acid solution. Some chromium salt of the acid was also obtained and the crude dicarboxylic acid was purified by boiling with sulphuric acid (1:1) before crystallisation.

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Received March 28, 1956.